

NDAC/LO/131
Feb 27, 1990

HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XII
by S. Söderhjelm, Lund Observatory

1. Introduction

Before continuing the work with the CHF-generation programs, it is apparent that they have to be tailored to the *real* contents of the Input Catalogue (which I have so far simulated rather ad hoc). The present note is therefore a preliminary (but laborious) study of the double and multiple stars in the actual Input Catalogue and its Annex 1. One aim is to test the completeness and consistency of the double and multiple star cataloguing principles adopted by INCA, but the checks performed so far are probably not exhaustive. Even this limited study raises however some questions that has to be investigated further.

All tests were initially done on the IC5 (July 1989), but after IC6 became available (Dec 1989), the work has been repeated. The original catalogues were obtained as 6250 bpi magnetic tapes, but in the further studies I have worked with the relevant parts of the data on direct access disc-files. No problems were encountered in reading the tapes.

2. Number statistics

In the Input Catalogue, each object has a three-digit multiplicity-code (plus a D/M to indicate a double/multiple system). The first digit gives the number of entries in the catalogue for a particular system, but because the definition of a 'system' may differ (see below), this is of little use. The second digit gives the number of components (within about $10''$) for an entry, while the third digit is zero (no special observing strategy) or 1(pr)/2(sec) for alternating observations. Counting the 'D/M xxx' combinations, there are 38 different types, and some care has to be exercised in defining suitable larger categories for the reductions.

The important point is the definition of a 'system'. A 'multiple' in the IC may be single or double (or multiple) in the reductions, depending on the brightness and spacing of the components, and this categorization is done before the Case History Files are created, using the data in the IC and its Annex1 (with data from the CCDM-catalogue). The following list of 'categories' gives a realistic picture of the actual number of known doubles and multiples that have to be treated. (The main category number gives the number of components that have to be treated, 3 for multiples, with small letters indicating temporary subgroups).

- 1a) For the great majority of IC entries (102233 out of 118272), the multiplicity code is zero, and these stars are thus not known as double or multiple. (This neglects any veiling glare effects, because they are at present *not* receiving any special treatment by NDAC. With the measured IFOV-profile at large r , *all* the flagged cases of VG have 'effective' magnitude differences above 3-4, and may therefore in practice be neglected).
- 1b) For another 3928 objects the last two digits of the multiplicity code are '10', meaning that although known wide (sep $>10''$) doubles/multiples, the extra

component(s) are faint ($\Delta m > 3$), and these stars may be treated in practice like the singles in 1a.

- 2a) The entries with multiplicity code 'D 120' are the known close doubles (separation $< 10''$), 7826 in total.
- 2b) For 974 doubles, there are two entries in the catalogue, with multiplicity code 'D211' for the primary and 'D212' for the secondary. These are the known wide (sep $> 10''$) doubles where the components are observed alternately. For another 54 'effective' wide doubles, the systems are not in the CCDM (multiplicity codes '-001/-002', '-001/D112', 'D111/-002').
- 2c) For 1106 multiples, the code ends in '20'. These known close multiples have only 2 components that need to be considered, and they are treated in practice like the close doubles in group 2a,
- 2d) There are 198 systems with codes 'Mx11/Mx12'. These known wide multiples have only two observed components, and are thus equivalent to group 2b.
- 3a) The 293 entries with multiplicity code 'M xn0' ($n > 2$) are the known close multiples with 3 or more components in a single pointing.
- 3b) There are 196 entries (with a variety of multiplicity codes) that corresponds to multiples with two IC entries observed alternately.
- 3c) Finally, for 14 systems, a common treatment is required for 3 separate IC entries.

All this adds up to 106161 'effective singles', 10158 'effective doubles' (11384 IC entries) and 503 'effective multiples' (727 IC entries). As will be seen below, the numbers of doubles and multiples are further reduced when the actual separations and magnitudes are considered.

3. Position data

The Input Catalogue gives a 'final' position for each entry. For doubles and multiples, these positions may be compared with the data given in Annex1, deriving from the CCDM-catalogue. A number of such comparisons have been performed, indicating some possible problems.

For close doubles (single IDT pointing), the IC position is agreed to be the primary position when $\Delta m > 1.2$ and the 'geometric' mean of the component positions when $\Delta m < 1.2$. (When individual positions are not available, the photocentre position may be selected instead). A straightforward comparison of the IC position with the primary, the photocentre and the geometric position from Annex 1 reveals first of all that the IC positions are in many cases several arcseconds from those in Annex 1, presumably due to more recent or accurate data. Using only the subset of the data where at least one of the Annex1 positions agrees within 1.0 arcsec with the IC position, we get the data in Table 1.

Table 1. Mean position deviations (arcsec, mean errors in parentheses) IC6-Annex1 for systems with maximum deviation 1 arcsec.

Sep(")	dm	n	pr diff	geom diff	pc diff
0-3	0-1.2	2446	0.39(0.27)	0.39(0.26)	0.39(0.26)
0-3	1.2-4	1413	0.40(0.26)	0.40(0.29)	0.40(0.26)
3-10	0-1.2	785	2.09(1.07)	0.80(0.83)	0.16(0.44)
3-10	1.2-4	1152	0.21(0.34)	2.89(1.08)	0.75(0.55)

As evident from these figures, no distinction between the different positions is possible for separations below 3 arcsec, because the Annex 1 then usually lists only a single common position for the two components. For separations above 3 arcsec, it is equally apparent that for large magnitude differences the primary position is selected in accordance with the rules above. For small magnitude differences, however, when the geometric position should be the norm, in most cases the photocentre is given instead. This is of some consequence in the photometric reductions, and the actual rules followed by INCA have to be specified.

For the wide doubles with alternate IDT pointings, a similar comparison of the Annex1 and IC positions for the two components reveals in general an almost perfect agreement. For some 5 % of these systems, the IC primary turns out to be the secondary in Annex1 (and vice versa). In most of these cases, the magnitude-differences are small, but there are a few which should be checked (see Section 5).

4. Separations and magnitudes

For the alternately observed doubles, the magnitude differences are (as expected) all below 3.0 mag, because otherwise the components are treated like independent singles. Most of the separations (85%) are in the range 10-30 arcsec, but there are some 4% above 40" and maximum values about 56". These large-separation doubles are in practice observed like single stars. The preliminary observed IFOV-profile (ESTEC.STATUS.04, Nov 29, 1989) confirms the on-ground calibration and gives an attenuation above 5 magnitudes at 30 arcsec. There is thus no point in keeping any system with larger separation, and 137 systems in group 2b and 32 systems in group 2d thus effectively make up 338 singles. For 52 (too) wide multiples in group 3b, the net result is 49 singles, 52 close doubles and 2 close multiples. For the '3-pointing' multiples in group 3c, only 5 systems have at least two of the three wide separations below 30 arcsec. The other 9 systems are transformed into 7 wide doubles, 2 close doubles, 1 '2-pointing' multiple and 9 singles.

For the closer doubles, there are many with such large Δm , that they will in practice need no double star treatment. A crude magnitude-dependent limit may be defined by

$$\Delta m = \begin{cases} 5.0 & H_p \leq 6 \\ 5.0 - 0.25(H_p - 6) & H_p > 6 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where one may safely assume that the doubles with fainter secondaries can be treated like singles. Checking the 8932 systems in groups 2a and 2c, we find 1288 that certainly fall outside the limit as against 7507 within. (The remaining 137 systems have unknown secondary magnitudes).

Fig. 1 shows the distribution of the 7079 close doubles with nonzero separations in the log sep/ Δm -plane. Because sep/ Δm are given in 0.1-steps, the sizes of the plotted symbols indicate the number of contributing systems (197 for 0.2 arcsec, $\Delta m=0.0$). In the upper left-hand region there is room for some new discoveries by SEEKDBL.

Also given in the IC is a parameter to indicate possible variability. Interestingly, for the 7826 systems in category 2a, 370 (4.7%) are suspected to be variable to some degree, but as many as 155 (14%) out of the 1106 in category 2c. This probably reflects a more thorough observation of the multiples, and if such a high figure holds generally, some additional procedure for testing the magnitude constancy should be included in the STDDBL program. (Exactly the same trend holds for the wide systems. Out of 974 in category 2b, 56 (5.7%) are variable, increasing to 25 (12.6%) for the 198 'double multiples' in category 2d).

5. Details and problems

A small number of multiplicity codes were incompatible with other data and had to be changed (no such cases were discovered for the IC5): IC-numbers 5795, 11918, 96688 and 116063 had the multiplicity code given as 'D111', but with no associated star. Only one component is given in Annex1, and they were therefore put in the 1b-category (code 'D110'). IC-# 20456 had code 'M121', but was moved to 'M120', because the only component given in Annex1 is a close one. For all (14) cases with three IDT-pointings, the multiplicity code ended in 2 for all three components. For the primaries given in Annex1, this was changed to a 1.

The following list gives some further statistical details and/or problems, sorted by the above categories.

- 2a) For this group, the data seem to be rather consistent, with all separations within 15 arcsec (only 5 above 12 arcsec). For 118 systems, no secondary magnitude is given in Annex1, and for half of these no separation either. (In most of these cases *some* indication of the magnitudes and separations should be available, even if the accuracy is low.) For another 303 systems, the magnitudes are given but not the separation, but for 297 of these, an 'O'-flag indicates that orbital elements will be given in a forthcoming Annex2. The Annex1 and IC-positions differ by more than 10 arcsec for 15 systems, the extreme cases being # 24366 (19" difference), # 74537 (20"), # 94249 (19"), # 99561 (31") and # 111221 (62" difference!). Only two systems have the Annex1 secondary brighter than the primary, for # 38256 by 1.6 magnitudes.

- 2b) The only major inconsistency is for IC# 19827/28, where the individual positions indicate 6 arcsec separation, but 11" is given in Annex 1. As stated in Section 3 above, there are also some cases with a faint 'primary' in Annex1 (=the secondary in the IC). The two extreme cases are # 52607/611 (H(pr)=10.07, H(sec)=7.50) and # 120059/60 (H(pr)=10.23, H(sec)=7.41), all others have $\Delta m < 1$ mag.
- 2c) As for the 2a-systems, the data are generally consistent. Again no separations above 15" are observed, but there are 19 pairs with unknown Δm , 5 of them with unknown separation. (For 116 out of 125 systems with no separation, the 'O'-flag indicates forthcoming orbital data). No systems have Annex1-positions more than 10" from the IC-position, and only two have 'faint primaries' in Annex1 (0.7 mag for # 3348).
- 2d) As for the 2b-cases, the only problems are some faint primaries in Annex1, but at most by 0.7 mag (# 120018/19).
- 3a) For the close multiples, the photocentres may be calculated from Annex1-data and compared with the positions given in the IC. The mean difference is about 1.2 arcsec, and only for # 28442 and # 44127 it reaches 10". At least one of the separations is zero in 28 systems, 27 of them with an 'O'-flag.
- 3b) The '2-pointing' multiples are a mixed collection of systems. No gross inconsistencies between the Annex1 and IC positions have been noted, but for # 39610 the discrepancy is 8 arcsec (while all other differences are below 3-4 arcsec).
- 3c) In the end, as seen above, only 5 multiples need three separate IDT-pointings. One of them is the Orion Trapezium, where Annex1 lists three quite unobservable 15-16:th mag components.

6. Conclusions

After a thorough reevaluation of the double-star data in the Input Catalogue, the number of 'known' systems to be processed is rather smaller than a priori expected. Although 15910 objects in the IC have a nonzero multiplicity code, only about 10426 need be considered in the double star reductions, making up some 8762 doubles and 445 multiples.

The presently available data is sufficient for collecting the IDT-data in suitable CHF-files (one for each double or multiple system), but the further improvement of the Annex1-data should start to be discussed. First, for the close systems now in Annex1, one would like to know what point (photocentre, geometric centre or primary) corresponds to the IC position. At present, mostly, neither of these positions calculated from Annex1-data coincides with the given IC-position. Secondly, some (however rough) values of $\text{sep}/\Delta m$ should be given where they are now missing completely. Also, Annex2 with orbital data should be completed. Thirdly, there are no doubt more known close (speckle-interferometric/astrometric/occultation) binaries not flagged in the IC. A (typical?) example is Algol AB-C (IC# 14576) which is now in category 1b with only the primary in Annex1 and no 'O'-flag.